

SHRINKAGE AND RETENTION BEHAVIOUR OF A CLAYEY SOIL TREATED WITH SUPERABSORBENT HYDROGELS

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In the Netherlands, flood protection is assured by a complex network of 18000 km of primary and secondary dykes. In recent years, concerns arose on the climate-sensitivity of the infrastructure subjected to drying-wetting cycles, overall temperature rise and drought periods not commonly experienced in the country before. All these factors can affect the serviceability and safety of infrastructures due to irreversible strains and desiccation cracks. Urban sprawl and densification in flood-prone low-lying areas also contribute to increasing the social and economic costs of the problem. A preliminary study has been initiated at TU Delft to assess the feasibility of superabsorbent hydrogels (SAH) as a mitigation measure and to increase soil resilience to drying. Thanks to their cross-linked three-dimensional network, superabsorbent hydrogels can absorb and retain large amounts of water and have been used in various fields such as drug delivery, food storage and hygiene products. In recent years, SAH are increasingly studied as possible soil amendment for drought in agriculture by virtue of their water retention capacity (Saha et al. 2020). In this study, a series of desiccation tests have been conducted to quantify the shrinkage and retention response of a clayey soil treated with SAH. The experimental results suggest a reduction in the evaporation rate for treated soil compared to the untreated one and at the expense of higher compressibility upon drying. The two effects contribute to altering the desiccation cracking mechanics with delayed cracks formation and lower cracked area. A modelling approach is also presented, which stems from the multiscale coupled models for compacted soils (Della Vecchia et al. 2013) to model the retention response of soil treated with SAH. The model will be used to eventually predict the response of earthworks to climate stresses and better assess the sensitivity of the infrastructure.

[1] Saha, A., Sekharan, S., & Manna, U. (2020). Superabsorbent hydrogel (SAH) as a soil amendment for drought management: A review. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 204, 104736.

[2] Della Vecchia, G., Jommi, C., and Romero, E. 2013. A fully coupled elastic-plastic hydromechanical model for compacted soils accounting for clay activity. *International Journal for Numerical and Analytical Methods in Geomechanics*, 37(5): 503-535.